

Duurzame financiering voor een duurzame Landbouw en Visserij

Informed Consent

I volunteer to participate in a research project conducted by Dr. Steven van Passel from Hasselt University. I understand that the project is designed to gather information about the market conditions for sugar beet farmers in Flanders. I will be one of approximately 15 people being interviewed for this research.

1. My participation in this project is voluntary. I understand that I will not be paid for my participation. I may withdraw and discontinue participation at any time without penalty. If I decline to participate or withdraw from the study, other participants will NOT be informed.

2. I understand that it is by no means intended to provoke me. If, however, I feel uncomfortable in any way during the interview session, I have the right to decline to answer any question or to end the interview.

3. Participation involves being interviewed by NAME OF INTERVIEWER from Hasselt University. The interview will be limited to 60 minutes. Notes will be written during the interview. An audio tape of the interview and subsequent dialogue will be made. If I don't want to be taped, I will not be able to participate in the study.

4. I understand that the researcher will not identify me by name in any reports using information obtained from this interview, and that my confidentiality as a participant in this study will remain secure. Subsequent uses of records and data will be subject to standard data use policies which protect the anonymity of individuals and institutions.

5. Other farmers or people involved in the sugar business will neither be present at the interview nor have access to raw notes, transcripts or translations. This precaution will prevent my individual comments from having any negative repercussions.

7. I have read and understand the explanation provided to me. I have had all my questions answered to my satisfaction, and I voluntarily agree to participate in this study.

8. I have been given a copy of this consent form.

My Signature Date

My Printed Name Signature of the Investigator

For further information, please contact:

Dr. [Name of Principle Researcher]

[Contact Information of PI!]

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